

Caregivers' Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices Related to Infant Feeding and Childhood Stunting in Ecuador: A Cross-Sectional Study.

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Abstract

Background/Objectives: Childhood chronic malnutrition (CCM) affects 17.5% of children under five years of age in Ecuador. This study aimed to characterize caregivers' Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices (KAP) regarding infant and young child feeding in order to identify critical factors influencing malnutrition across six provinces of the country. **Methods:** An observational, cross-sectional study was conducted involving 1053 caregivers. Standardized modules from the FAO KAP questionnaire were applied, and nutritional status was assessed using World Health Organization (WHO) growth standards. **Results:** The prevalence of CCM increased progressively with age, reaching 64.7% among children aged 4–5 years. A substantial gap was identified between knowledge (75.7%) and the adequate practice of breastfeeding (47.6%) among infants under six months of age. Minimum dietary diversity was alarmingly low, with only 13.5% of children aged 6–23 months achieving adequate intake. Notably, no statistically significant association was found between KAP levels and the degree of malnutrition, suggesting that structural barriers outweigh knowledge-related factors. **Conclusions:** A clear dissociation exists between high self-reported knowledge and the implementation of optimal feeding practices. Interventions aimed at reducing CCM in Ecuador must go beyond traditional nutrition education and focus on behavioral empowerment and the mitigation of structural and socioeconomic barriers.

Keywords: Malnutrition; Child, Preschool; Infant; Nutritional Status, Caregivers.

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1. Introduction

Childhood chronic malnutrition (CCM) affects 23.2% of children under five years of age worldwide, while Latin America and the Caribbean account for 12.4% [1]. In Ecuador, the second round of the National Survey on Child Malnutrition (ENDI) conducted in 2023 reported a national prevalence of 17.5%[2]. This condition does not solely reflect inadequate dietary intake, but rather results from a complex interplay of factors, including limited parental or caregiver knowledge and food insecurity[3].

Caregivers' Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices (KAP) related to child feeding constitute fundamental determinants of child nutritional status. Inadequate application of nutrition-related knowledge has been shown to be a significant predictor of malnutrition

in low- and middle-income countries. In this context, the role of caregivers is critical, as their practices—including breastfeeding (BF) and dietary diversity—define the intake of essential nutrients. Likewise, food security and hygiene are crucial, as inadequate practices in these areas compromise the quality of complementary feeding, increase the risk of diarrheal diseases, and consequently exacerbate malnutrition[4].

The World Health Organization (WHO) recommends that children aged 6–23 months receive a varied diet during the complementary feeding (CF) period to ensure adequate nutritional intake. The KAP questionnaire specifically includes a section that assesses Minimum Dietary Diversity (MDD), which is a strong predictor of diet quality and has been validated as an indicator for evaluating micronutrient deficiencies[5]. The previous WHO 2008 MDD indicator used seven food groups and did not include breast milk as a food source, which disadvantaged breastfed children compared to formula-fed children when assessing diet quality. Consequently, indicators calculated using the former method are not comparable with those derived from the updated approach[6].

Furthermore, dietary diversity has been associated with improved linear growth in children, as poor dietary diversity increases the risk of micronutrient deficiencies, potentially affecting physical and cognitive development. Minimum dietary diversity has been shown to be positively associated with mean micronutrient adequacy of the diet[5].

Neurodevelopment is a complex process of neuronal scaffolding, as the formation of increasingly complex neural circuits depends on the successful completion of earlier developmental stages. This synchronization is critical because failure at a specific developmental sequence may result in irreversible loss of function due to complex processes involving structural and cellular changes in the brain[7] [8]. Accordingly, evidence has documented the effects of nutrition in early life on neurodevelopment. Adequate nutrient intake is essential for processes such as myelination, synaptogenesis, and neurotransmitter production.

Conversely, the negative effects of inadequate nutrition on neurodevelopment are often irreversible, leading to lifelong impairments in cognitive development and mental health [9]. A systematic review and meta-analysis conducted by Kirolos in 2022 provided strong evidence of the association between malnutrition and impaired neurodevelopment, measured using the Denver-II test across fine motor, gross motor, language, and personal–social domains, compared with controls from low- and middle-income countries [10]. Addressing health needs in the child population is therefore imperative to prevent growth and developmental impairments that may manifest in both the short and long term [11].

The present study aims to describe feeding practices through the application of the KAP framework among caregivers of children under five years of age, grouped by age categories (under 6 months, 6–23 months, and children older than 24 months), across six provinces of Ecuador. The objective is to identify critical factors requiring intervention, as well as the characteristics of such interventions, based on indicators derived from feeding practices and childhood malnutrition.

2. Methods

The study was observational, descriptive, and prospective, conducted during 2024, and framed within the baseline of the Playful Learning Landscapes (PLL) project for the Prevention of CCM. The reference population corresponds to the National Strategy “Ecuador Grows Without Malnutrition.”

The study was based on data collected through a survey administered to families with children under six years of age. Structured questions derived from internationally

standardized modules were applied to caregivers of children under six years, and anthropometric measurements (weight and height) were obtained from the children, following the acquisition of written informed consent duly signed by their caregivers.

The survey was administered to families at locations where they were convened through mass outreach activities. These locations included areas in and around municipal markets, open-air markets, and community spaces. The activities were conducted with direct support from local authorities and community leaders, who participated in a total of 12 outreach caravans.

Data analysis was performed using a quantitative approach, combining descriptive and comparative analyses. Initially, frequency tables, percentages, and descriptive measures were generated to characterize the study population and to describe caregivers' levels of KAP.

Subsequently, the normality of quantitative variables was assessed using the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test. As the results indicated non-normal distributions, the nonparametric Wilcoxon test was applied to compare mean differences between groups according to sociodemographic and nutritional characteristics, including child age group, geographic region, caregiver sex, and level of chronic malnutrition. A significance level of 5% was considered ($p < 0.05$).

2.1 Study population

The study population consisted of caregivers and children under six years of age from families residing in nine rural and urban parishes across six provinces of Ecuador. These areas were identified by the National Strategy “Ecuador Grows Without Malnutrition” as having a higher prevalence of childhood chronic malnutrition and elevated levels of poverty measured by unmet basic needs (UBN) [7]. The selected sample was non-probabilistic, as data were collected from families who voluntarily agreed to provide information and who were participants in the PAL project. Table 1 presents the data collection sites.

Table 1. Data collection sites

PROVINCE	CANTON	PARISH	n	%
Bolívar	Guaranda	Simiátug	61	5.8
Chimborazo	Guamote	Cebadas	106	10.1
		Palmira	58	5.5
Esmeraldas	Muisne	San Gregorio	241	22.9
Morona Santiago	Tiwindza	Santiago	30	2.8
		San José	112	10.6
Pastaza	Pastaza	Canelos	56	5.3
		Simón Bolívar	60	5.7
Santa Elena	Santa Elena	Colonche	329	31.2
TOTAL			1053	

2.2 Metical approval

The protocol was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki. Participation was voluntary, and written informed consent was obtained from the legal representatives prior to data collection and before inclusion in the study. The database used for analysis was anonymized prior to data processing.

2.3 Inclusion criteria

All primary caregivers of children under five years of age who resided in the selected parishes, attended the outreach activities, and provided written informed consent were included in the study.

2.4 Exclusion criteria

Individuals residing in the community who presented communication difficulties that hindered the correct administration of the instrument were excluded from the study.

2.5 Data collection process

A structured interviewer-administered survey was conducted, based on the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) guidelines for the assessment of nutrition-related Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices (KAP) [6].

In the first section of the questionnaire, comprising 10 questions, seven were related to caregiver information and three to child information. The sociodemographic variables collected for caregivers included age, educational level, ethnic identification, marital status, and household composition, while child-related variables included age and sex. The survey consists of 13 modules; however, in this initial phase, the first three modules related to feeding and nutrition in children under five years of age were used: feeding of children under 6 months (Module 1), feeding of children aged 6–23 months (Module 2), feeding of preschool-aged children (24–59 months; Module 3), and malnutrition (Module 5).

In addition, children's nutritional status was assessed using data obtained from anthropometric measurements conducted *in situ* by qualified health personnel using standardized equipment (scales, infantometers/child stadiometers, and measuring tapes). Nutritional status was interpreted through the calculation of indicators such as weight-for-age, height-for-age, and head circumference-for-age, according to World Health Organization (WHO) growth standards, and classified as normal, chronic malnutrition (stunting), or overweight [10].

Based on the modules analyzed, the following analytical groups were defined: children under 6 months; infants older than 6 months and younger than 23 months; children older than 24 months (preschool-aged); and children with chronic malnutrition. All groups were analyzed using an approach based on questions designed to identify children's knowledge, attitudes, and practices as reported by their caregivers.

Regarding knowledge-related questions, responses were classified as adequate when respondents provided one, several, or all of the correct answers, and as inadequate when no correct answers were provided. Subsequently, knowledge indicators were calculated to classify the population's KAP levels according to the number of correct responses.

According to the FAO guidelines for nutrition-related KAP assessment, the urgent implementation of nutrition education is recommended when results are $\leq 70\%$; an intervention should be considered when results range between 71% and 89%; and intervention is not considered necessary or is difficult to justify when results are $\geq 90\%$ of correct responses, optimal practices, or desired/positive attitudes within the surveyed population[4].

2.5.1 Feeding knowledge

In this section, information was collected on BF practices and feeding frequency (4 items), as well as on topics related to knowledge of protein intake (7 items), fat intake (7 items), vitamin intake (13 items), calcium intake (4 items), dietary fiber intake (9 items), essential nutrients (3 items), and child nutrition (10 items).

2.5.2 Attitudes related to practices for adequate nutrition

Attitudes were assessed by evaluating perceived benefits, perceived barriers, and self-efficacy for exclusive BF with breast milk among infants under six months of age, as well as attitudes toward feeding recommendations for children aged 6–24 months and those older than 24 months. The scores obtained were classified as adequate or inadequate according to cutoff points defined during the instrument validation process.

2.5.3 Feeding practices

Practices were assessed based on self-reported practices or behaviors related to BF and the introduction of liquids among infants under six months of age; feeding frequency and dietary diversity among children aged 6–24 months; and feeding frequency, timing, and place of food intake among children older than 24 months, in accordance with indicators recommended by the World Health Organization (WHO) and the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO).

2.5.3.1 Minimum dietary diversity

In Module 2, information on dietary diversity among children aged 6–23 months was collected. This was assessed through a survey on foods and beverages consumed during the previous day. According to the updated definition of the MDD indicator (WHO, 2021), MDD is defined as the percentage of children aged 6–23 months who consumed foods and beverages from at least five of the eight food groups during the previous day. The eight food groups used to calculate this indicator are:

1. Breast milk
2. Grains, roots, tubers, and plantains
3. Legumes (beans, peas, lentils), nuts, and seeds
4. Dairy products (milk, infant formula, yogurt, cheese)
5. Flesh foods (meat, fish, poultry, organ meats)
6. Eggs
7. Vitamin A-rich fruits and vegetables
8. Other fruits and vegetables

(Indicators for assessing infant and young child feeding practices: definitions and measurement methods. Geneva: World Health Organization and the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF), 2021. Licence: CC BY- NC-SA 3.0 IGO; <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/3.0/igo/>.)

3. Results

4.1 Subgroup analysis: Sociodemographics

The distribution of the analyzed cases reflects the demographic composition of the households benefiting from the project and serves as the starting point for analyzing characteristics and conditions associated with growth, development, and caregiving practices during the early years of life. The case structure is as follows:

- Under 6 months: 126 (12.0%)
- 6–23 months: 406 (38.6%)
- Over 24 months: 521 (49.5%)

The distribution is heterogeneous, as participant selection depended on families’ willingness to participate in the project. A higher concentration of participants was observed in the older age groups, particularly among children older than 24 months. Infants under 6 months represented the smallest proportion of the sample, accounting for 12.0% of the total.

Across the three regions, a similar proportional distribution was observed, with children older than 24 months constituting the predominant group (49.5%). In the Sierra region, this group accounted for 50.2%, while in the Coast it represented 45.8%, and in the Amazon region it reached the highest proportion (57.0%), indicating a greater presence of older children in this region.

The intermediate group, consisting of children aged 6–23 months (38.6%), maintained a substantial representation across all regions. The Coast showed the highest proportion (41.1%), followed by the Sierra (36.9%) and the Amazon (34.5%). This pattern reflects the high presence of young children in households in the Coast region (n = 570), consistent with the distribution presented in Table 2.

In contrast, children under 6 months constituted the smallest segment in all regions, representing 12.9% in the Sierra, 13.2% in the Coast, and 8.5% in the Amazon. Although the distribution was relatively homogeneous, the comparatively lower percentage observed in the Amazon region is noteworthy.

Table 2. Percentage distribution of boys and girls by region and age group.

Age groups	Region						Total	
	Sierra		Cost		Amazon		n	%
	n	%	n	%	n	%		
Under 6 months	29	12,9	75	13,2	22	8,5	126	12,0
6–23 months	83	36,9	234	41,1	89	34,5	406	38,6
Over 24 months	113	50,2	261	45,8	147	57,0	521	49,5
Total	225	100,0	570	100,0	258	100,0	1053	100,0

According to caregiver sex (father, mother, guardian, etc.), the vast majority of caregivers were female (95.3%), while only 4.7% were male. This finding highlights the predominance of women as the primary providers of child care in the surveyed households.

The age groups in which a relatively higher presence of male caregivers was observed were those of children aged 6–23 months and those older than 24 months (Table 3).

Table 3. Percentage distribution of boys and girls by age group and caregiver sex.

Age Groups	Caregiver sex		Total
	Male	Female	

Under 6 months	n	5	121	126
	%	4.0	96.0	100.0
6–23 months	n	20	386	406
	%	4.9	95.1	100.0
Over 24 months	n	24	497	521
	%	4.6	95.4	100.0
Total	n	49	1004	1053
	%	4.7	95.3	100.0

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4.2 Subgroup analysis: Nutricional status

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Figure 1 shows the percentage distribution of moderate chronic malnutrition (HAZ -2) by age group. A progressive increase in the prevalence of chronic malnutrition is observed as children grow older, with moderate chronic malnutrition reaching its highest value in the 4–5-year age group (46.2%). Among children under one year of age, the lowest prevalence was observed (22.7%). This pattern suggests an accumulation of nutritional deficits over time, indicating that chronic malnutrition tends to intensify with age when timely and sustained interventions are not implemented.

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Figure 1. Percentage distribution of chronic malnutrition by age group.

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4.3 Subgroup analysis: KAP by Evaluated Modules

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To identify the levels of Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices (KAP) among project participants, mean scores were calculated based on the proportion of caregivers who reported positive responses within each group of questions comprising the respective modules. Table 4 presents the results according to participants' sociodemographic and nutritional characteristics, as well as the statistical significance values derived from comparisons of mean scores between groups.

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The highest level of knowledge was observed among caregivers of children older than 24 months (81.8%), compared with those caring for children under 6 months (75.7%) and those aged 6–23 months (73.6%). However, these differences were not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). Similarly, attitudes showed relatively stable levels across age groups (42.1%–46.1%), with no significant differences, although the highest percentage was again observed among caregivers of children older than 24 months (46.1%). Practices, however, exhibited greater variability: only 32.5% of caregivers of children aged 6–23 months reported adequate practices, whereas this proportion increased to 63.2% among caregivers of children older than two years. Nevertheless, these differences did not reach statistical significance ($p > 0.05$). Overall, these findings indicate that as children grow older, caregivers tend to develop greater confidence and consistency in implementing appropriate practices, even when differences in knowledge levels are not pronounced.

Regarding geographic location, caregivers residing in the Sierra region demonstrated higher knowledge levels (72.5%) compared with those living in the Coast (64.1%) and the Amazon region (65.7%). Statistically significant differences in knowledge were identified between the Sierra and the Coast, as well as between the Sierra and the Amazon ($p < 0.05$). Caregivers from the Coast exhibited the highest levels of positive attitudes (52.3%), surpassing those from the Sierra (50.1%) and the Amazon (50.4%), with a significant difference observed between the Sierra and Amazon regions ($p = 0.014$). In terms of practices, the Sierra region showed the highest percentage (61.6%), followed by the Coast (59.1%) and the Amazon (57.7%); however, no statistically significant differences were found among regions ($p > 0.05$). These results indicate that the Sierra region not only includes a larger number of participants but also demonstrates more favorable levels across all three components of the KAP framework.

Additionally, women exhibited slightly higher knowledge levels (71.0%) than men (69.2%), with a difference of 1.8 percentage points. In contrast, attitudes were marginally higher among men (57.0%) compared with women (56.5%). Practices were also similar between both groups (62.0% in men and 60.9% in women). Although male participation in the sample was low (4.6%), these findings suggest that when caregivers are male, their adherence to appropriate practices is comparable to, or even slightly higher than, that of female caregivers. None of the observed differences across the three KAP components were statistically significant ($p > 0.05$).

Table 4. Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices (KAP) by sociodemographic characteristics according to questionnaire modules.

Groups/Characteristics	n	Knowledge		Attitudes		Practices	
		Mean diff**		Mean diff**		Mean diff**	
		%	p-value	%	p-value	%	p-value
<i>Ages Groups</i>							
Under 6 months	126	75.7	0.873	42.2	0.994	47.6	0.619
6–23 months	406	73.6	0.667	42.1	0.820	32.5	0.429
Over 24 months	521	81.8	0.765	46.1	0.804	63.2	0.152
<i>Geographic region</i>							
Cost	225	64.1	0.001*	52.3	0.795	59.1	0.953
Sierra	570	72.5	0.232	50.1	0.014*	61.6	0.098
Amazon region	258	65.7	0.001*	50.4	0.065	57.7	0.769
<i>Caregiver sex</i>							
Male	49	69.2	0.322	57.0	0.277	62.0	0.624

Female 1004 71.0 56.5 60.9

* *p*-value < 0.05 considered to be statistically significant.

4.4 Subgroup analysis: Perceived attitudes

Table 5 shows that, based on mean scores, caregivers reported high levels of confidence in their ability to perform appropriate caregiving practices across all age groups: 88.6% among caregivers of children under 6 months, 87.0% among those caring for children aged 6–23 months, and 85.1% among caregivers of children older than 24 months. Perceived barriers were low (4.4%–7.0%), indicating that few caregivers explicitly recognized difficulties in implementing the recommended practices.

Regarding perceptions of dietary intake, 19.8% of caregivers of children under 6 months perceived intake as sufficient, whereas 7.9% reported low intake. Among children aged 6–23 months, 17.0% of caregivers perceived intake as adequate and 16.0% reported low intake. These findings indicate that, despite high levels of confidence, perceptions of dietary intake vary according to the child’s stage of growth.

Table 5. Attitudes toward feeding by age group (months).

Age groups	Outcomes	n	%
Under 6 months	Confidence	112	88.6
	Barriers	7	5.2
	Sufficient intake	25	19.8
	Low intake	10	7.9
6–23 months	Confidence	353	87.0
	Barriers	18	4.4
	Adequate intake	69	17.0
	Low intake	65	16.0
Over 24 months	Confidence	444	85.1
	Barriers	37	7.0

4.5 Subgroup analysis: Minimum dietary diversity

The assessment of MDD revealed that only 13.5% of children achieved adequate intake (≥5 different food groups, including breast milk), while 86.5% exhibited inadequate dietary diversity, consuming fewer than four food groups. This finding indicates low dietary diversity in the assessed child population, representing a relevant risk factor for nutritional quality and the prevention of chronic malnutrition.

Table 6. Dietary diversity practices among children aged 6–23 months.

Results	Categories	n	%
Adequate	Five or more different food groups in the diet, including breast milk	56	13.5
Inadequate	Fewer than four food groups in the diet	350	86.5

4. Discussion

The KAP questionnaire is a validated and widely used public health tool for identifying modifiable behaviors that can affect children throughout their life course, primarily impacting health, education, and productivity outcomes [12]. Under the KAP framework, higher levels of knowledge are expected to translate into healthier feeding behaviors and, consequently, improved child nutritional status, thereby reducing mortality and disease burden associated with malnutrition.

Regarding nutritional status, childhood chronic malnutrition (CCM) showed an increasing trend with age, with a mean age of 2 years (SD = 1.12). Among children under one year of age, stunting (HAZ < -2) was observed in 22.7%, increasing to 64.7% among children aged 4–5 years. Similarly, a study conducted in Chimborazo reported a CCM prevalence of 51.6%, with 34.43% among children under one year of age and a progressive increase to 64.37% in the 25–36-month age group [13]. These findings reinforce evidence of cumulative nutritional deficits as children age.

In terms of demographic characteristics, caregivers were predominantly women (95.3%), primarily mothers (89.7%). Women demonstrated knowledge levels that were 1.8 percentage points higher than those of male caregivers. In contrast, a study conducted among working women in India found that only 29% demonstrated adequate knowledge, attitudes, and practices related to child feeding [14]. Another study in a rural Ecuadorian community reported that although 77.89% of caregivers had adequate knowledge regarding complementary feeding, only 55.96% implemented appropriate practices [15]. This gap between knowledge and practice highlights the influence of contextual and structural factors beyond individual knowledge.

In the present study, KAP was analyzed across four regions of Ecuador. The regional analysis showed that the Sierra region consistently achieved higher scores in the Knowledge domain (72.5%); however, a notable reduction of 10.9 percentage points was observed in Practices (61.6%) compared with the Coast and Amazon regions. Notably, despite having lower knowledge levels (64.1%), the Coast region reported the highest Attitude scores (52.3%), suggesting a positive disposition toward change that may not be fully leveraged due to limited technical knowledge or resources. Similarly, research conducted in Assam, India, confirmed that children whose mothers had low KAP levels were 2.05 times more likely to experience stunting compared with those whose mothers had high KAP levels [14].

Exclusive BF, as recommended by the World Health Organization (WHO) and several pediatric societies for approximately the first six months of life, reduces infant mortality by 33% and lowers the risk of other diseases in low- and middle-income countries [16]. In this study, among children under six months of age, a substantial gap was observed between knowledge (75.7%) and appropriate BF practices (47.6%). Despite high levels of knowledge and self-efficacy (88.6%), only 19.8% of caregivers perceived that they were providing sufficient breast milk. This discrepancy may be driven by sociocultural factors, social pressure for early food introduction, and maternal working conditions, highlighting the need for targeted interventions during this critical period.

CF is defined as the process of introducing foods when breast milk alone is no longer sufficient to meet the infant's nutritional requirements [17,18]. Higher levels of knowledge and adequate feeding practices were identified among caregivers of children older than 24 months (81.8% and 63.2%, respectively). However, among children aged 6–23 months, these indicators declined sharply, with practices dropping from 73.6% to 32.5%, reflecting logistical and resource-related constraints that traditional educational interventions fail to overcome, despite self-efficacy levels exceeding 85%. These barriers appear to be structural, attitudinal, or related to parenting demands rather than cognitive limitations. As

children grow older, caregivers tend to gain confidence, consistent with previous literature indicating that integration into the family diet reduces certain preparation barriers, although this does not guarantee adequate dietary quality [19]. Nevertheless, these practice levels remain insufficient given the high prevalence of CCM in this group (69.4% moderate and 67.2% severe).

As part of CF, MDD is associated with improved linear growth and a lower risk of micronutrient deficiencies, which can lead to adverse physical and cognitive outcomes [6]. In this study, MDD was low, with only 13.5% of children achieving adequate consumption of five or more food groups. This figure is lower than that reported in a meta-analysis from Ethiopia (25.69%; 95% CI: 11.96–39.41), aligning with studies showing that inadequate MDD increases the risk of stunting, wasting, and underweight [20]. The observed dissociation between high knowledge and poor practices mirrors findings from other low- and middle-income countries, where structural factors and household dynamics outweigh knowledge in shaping feeding behaviors.

Finally, a relevant finding was that across all three age groups, attitudes did not function as a bridge between knowledge and practice. In several instances, attitude scores were even lower than knowledge scores, suggesting low perceived self-efficacy and doubts regarding the feasibility of nutritional recommendations in vulnerable contexts. This underscores the need for strategies that move beyond information-based approaches toward interventions focused on behavioral empowerment, while accounting for available resources and cultural beliefs.

4.1 Study limitations

A key strength of this study is that it establishes a baseline for characterizing caregivers' feeding behaviors across three regions of Ecuador, segmented by critical physiological stages of infant and young child feeding. Nevertheless, several important limitations should be acknowledged. First, the study employed non-probabilistic sampling and did not define an *a priori* sample size. Given the voluntary nature of participation, the results may be subject to selection bias, thereby limiting generalizability due to potential systematic differences between participating households and those that declined to participate. Second, some terms from the original KAP questionnaire were not fully adapted to regional linguistic variations, which may have influenced caregivers' interpretation of certain questions.

5. Conclusions

The results reveal a persistent gap between caregivers' knowledge, attitudes, and feeding practices across different regions of Ecuador. These findings suggest that strategies to reduce childhood chronic malnutrition should not focus solely on addressing knowledge deficits, but rather on implementing actions that strengthen structural, affective, and behavioral components.

The limited adequacy of feeding practices after six months of age suggests that resource constraints, sociocultural barriers, and family dynamics hinder the implementation of appropriate feeding, even when favorable attitudes are present. Additionally, a greater lack of knowledge regarding feeding processes was identified among male caregivers, indicating that shared responsibility in child-rearing remains an area requiring further action and parental involvement. This highlights the need for exploratory studies on parenting styles and feeding behaviors as constructs of social interaction.

Finally, these findings underscore the urgency of implementing comprehensive interventions that address the real barriers identified, with an emphasis on strengthening

attitudes and practices related to feeding. Such interventions should recognize the critical importance of nutrition in the early years of life and its preventable effects on neurodevelopment, thereby contributing to improved child well-being in Ecuador.

6. Patents

Author Contributions: Conceptualization, M.A.; methodology, M.A.; software, Y.V.; formal analysis, Y.V.; data curation, J.S.; data collection, P.R.; writing—original draft preparation, M.A. and Y.V.; writing—review and editing, M.A.; project administration, M.A.; funding acquisition, P.R.; validation, Y.V.; All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Informed Consent Statement: Informed consent was obtained from all subjects involved in the study. The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and approved by the Institutional Review Board (or Ethics Committee) of Universidad de Cuenca protocol code CEISH-UC-2023-436, approved on 27/09/2023.

Data Availability Statement: The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author. The data are not publicly available due to privacy and ethical restrictions regarding the sensitive nature of the information collected from households and minor participants.

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Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

ENDI	National Survey on Child Malnutrition
CCM	Childhood chronic malnutrition
KAP	Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices
WHO	World Health Organization
CF	Complementary Feeding
BF	Breast Feeding
MDD	Minimum Dietary Diversity
PLL	Playful Learning Landscapes
HAZ	Height for age z score

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